

Agricultural Technical Coefficients of IO Models that use Natural Resources

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Abstract

The research focuses on the input-output (IO) model for economies strongly dependent on natural resources. A novel methodology is proposed to compute the technical coefficients, based on real data, of the agricultural sector of Argentina. The methodology is compared with the one currently followed in the National Accounts Office. In the course of the investigation, a shadow supply function based on the random provision of natural resources is developed.

Key Words: input-output model, natural resources, land.

1. Leontief's IO Model

Let us consider a balanced economy in which total supply of products equals to the sum of total demand of inputs (or intermediate demand) and final consumption. That is, an economy in which the following identity is satisfied

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{1}_k = \mathbf{D}_I \mathbf{1}_k + \mathbf{D}_F \mathbf{1}_q = \mathbf{d}_I + \mathbf{d}_F, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{S} is a supply tableau of n products by k sectors, \mathbf{D}_I is an intermediate demand tableau of the same dimensions and \mathbf{D}_F is an analogous tableau, but for q final demandants. If we define a diagonal matrix \mathbf{T}_k^{-1} , whose j -th diagonal element is the inverse of the total supply of the j -th industry, we can rewrite the previous identity as

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{1}_k = \mathbf{D}_I \mathbf{T}_k^{-1} \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{1}_n + \mathbf{D}_F \mathbf{1}_q$$

as $\mathbf{T}_k^{-1} \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{1}_n = \mathbf{1}_k$. If, in addition, we premultiply both sides of the identity by $\mathbf{S}' \mathbf{T}_n^{-1}$, where \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} is a matrix analogous to \mathbf{T}_k^{-1} , but replacing the industry totals with product totals, we get

$$\mathbf{S}' (\mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{1}_k) = (\mathbf{S}' \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{D}_I \mathbf{T}_k^{-1}) \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{1}_n + (\mathbf{S}' \mathbf{T}_n^{-1}) \mathbf{D}_F \mathbf{1}_q, \quad (2)$$

or, calling $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{1}_k$,

$$\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1} [(\mathbf{S}' \mathbf{T}_n^{-1}) \mathbf{d}_F], \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the so-called matrix of direct production requirements, or technological matrix, and $(\mathbf{S}' \mathbf{T}_n^{-1}) \mathbf{d}_F$ is the final demand expressed by industry. Matrix $(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1}$ is known as the direct and indirect production requirements matrix, or Leontief's inverse matrix, or matrix of multipliers.

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Model (3) can be reformulated by pre-multiplying both sides of the equality by a vector of prices (or price indices) by industry

$$\mathbf{p}'\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{p}'(\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1})\mathbf{d}_F = \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + [\mathbf{p}'(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})]\mathbf{x}. \quad (4)$$

Canceling the industry supply vectors \mathbf{x} , calling the vector in brackets \mathbf{v}' (by gross value added), transposing both sides of the equality and rearranging, we get the version dual model pricing (3)

$$\mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A}')^{-1}\mathbf{v}, \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}_k^+. \quad (5)$$

More over, value added can be calculated from non-produced factors (essentially labor and capital) by appealing to the relationship $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B}_k\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{B}'_k\boldsymbol{\pi}$, where \mathbf{y} is a vector of quantities of non-produced factors used by the industry, $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ is a vector of prices of these factors and \mathbf{B}_k is a matrix of technical coefficients. The incorporation of factors leads to the model

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B}_k(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1}(\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1})\mathbf{d}_F \\ \mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A}')^{-1}\mathbf{B}'_k\boldsymbol{\pi} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The traditional IO model, in either (3) or (5) version, is inadequate to describe economies strongly dependent on natural resources (NR) because it only considers the supply of produced inputs. In fact, the provision of natural resources is excluded from the model. To remedy this drawback, Frank (2022) proposed a version of the IO model specific for economies dependent on NR, as the argentinian economy.¹

2. Exogenous Production

The model proposed by Frank (2022) incorporates the exogenous provision of NR through an additional “industry” called *land*, but maintains the original logic of the IO model regarding endogenous production.² This reformulation, however, requires that the technical coefficients associated with the provision and/or absorption of NR be known, which rarely happens in practice. A simpler and even more feasible formulation from a projection standpoint would consist of separating into blocks those sectors whose production is exogenous to the model and operate with them as proxy variables of *land*.

2.1 Decomposition into sectoral blocks

In order to separate exogenous from endogenous production we will appeal to the following proposition.

Proposition (Decomposition of the IO model into blocks). Leontief’s IO model can be decomposed in such a way that the supply of a sectorial block can be expressed as a function of the final demand of it’s own products and the supply of another block.

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}(\mathbf{S}'_1\mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{d}_1^F) + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{A}_{12}\mathbf{x}_2 \\ \mathbf{p}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1}(\mathbf{B}'_{11}\boldsymbol{\pi}_1 + \mathbf{B}'_{21}\boldsymbol{\pi}_2) + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{A}'_{21}\mathbf{p}_2 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

¹For further details on the IO model, we recommend the texts of Miller & Blair (2009) and tenRaa (2005).

²For an exhaustive review of the role of land in the production function, see Hubacek & van den Bergh (2002).

Proof. Let us consider a matrix of direct and indirect requirements partitioned into four blocks originated in turn in the following partitions of the Supply and Use Tableaux (TSU)

$$\mathbf{S} = [\mathbf{S}_1 \quad \mathbf{S}_2] \quad y \quad \mathbf{D}_1 = [\mathbf{D}_1 \quad \mathbf{D}_2].$$

where \mathbf{S}_1 and \mathbf{D}_1 are matrices of dimension $n \times r$, while \mathbf{S}_2 and \mathbf{D}_2 have dimension $n \times (k - r)$. Then, the matrix of direct and indirect requirements is

$$(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11} & -\mathbf{A}_{12} \\ -\mathbf{A}_{21} & \mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{11} & \mathbf{U}_{12} \\ \mathbf{U}_{21} & \mathbf{U}_{22} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

- (a) The IO model that arises from this partition, appealing to the formulas given by Tzon-Tzer & Shenh-Hua (2002) to invert a block matrix, is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1 \\ \mathbf{x}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{11} & (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{12} \mathbf{U}_{22} \\ (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{21} \mathbf{U}_{11} & \mathbf{U}_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}'_1 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^F \\ \mathbf{S}'_2 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_2^F \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

If we isolate $\mathbf{U}_{22} (\mathbf{S}'_2 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_2^F)$ in the second equation and replace it by $\mathbf{x}_2 - (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{21} \mathbf{U}_{11} (\mathbf{S}'_1 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^F)$ in the first equation; we also replace $\mathbf{A}_{12} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{21}$ by $(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11}) - \mathbf{U}_{11}^{-1}$; and cancel out superfluous terms

$$\mathbf{x}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} (\mathbf{S}'_1 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^F) + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{12} \mathbf{x}_2. \quad (10)$$

- (b) The price-dual version is obtained in a similar fashion although the algebra involved in the deduction is a bit more laborious. The trasposed matrix of direct and indirect requirements is

$$(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A}')^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}'_{11} & \mathbf{U}'_{11} \mathbf{A}'_{21} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \\ \mathbf{U}'_{22} \mathbf{A}'_{12} (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} & \mathbf{U}'_{22} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

Then,

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{p}_1 = \mathbf{U}'_{11} \mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{U}'_{11} \mathbf{A}'_{21} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{v}_2 \\ \mathbf{p}_2 = \mathbf{U}'_{22} \mathbf{A}'_{12} (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{U}'_{22} \mathbf{v}_2 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Isolating \mathbf{v}_2 from the second equation (assuming that the inverse of \mathbf{U}'_{22} exists) leads to

$$\mathbf{p}_1 = \mathbf{U}'_{11} [\mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{A}'_{21} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} (\mathbf{U}'_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{p}_2 - \mathbf{C} (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{v}_1], \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{A}'_{21} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_{12}$. The expansion of \mathbf{U}_{11} given by Tzon-Tzer & Shenh-Hua (2002) leads in turn to the identity

$$\mathbf{A}'_{21} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_{12} = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11}) - (\mathbf{U}'_{11})^{-1} \quad (14)$$

So, replacing \mathbf{C} by $\mathbf{I}_r - (\mathbf{U}'_{11})^{-1}$ in (13) and rearranging the expression conveniently we get

$$\mathbf{p}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{v}_1 + [\mathbf{U}'_{11} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} (\mathbf{U}'_{22})^{-1}] \mathbf{p}_2. \quad (15)$$

Matrix $(\mathbf{U}'_{22})^{-1}$ can be decomposed in terms of \mathbf{A}_{ij} recalling again the formulas given by Tzon-Tzer & Shenh-Hua, so that the matrix between brackets in the expression above can be rewritten as $\mathbf{U}'_{11} [\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{C} (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1}] \mathbf{A}'_{21}$. Besides, $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{I}_r - (\mathbf{U}'_{11})^{-1}$ so, after replacing in (13), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}_1 &= (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{v}_1 + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_{21} \mathbf{p}_2 \\ &= (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} (\mathbf{B}'_{11} \boldsymbol{\pi}_1 + \mathbf{B}'_{21} \boldsymbol{\pi}_2) + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_{21} \mathbf{p}_2. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

- (c) The formulas for \mathbf{x}_2 and \mathbf{p}_2 follow by symmetry. The reader can verify that by exchanging the order of the blocks in the TSU the blocks of \mathbf{A} are relocated in the following fashion

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{22} & \mathbf{A}_{21} \\ \mathbf{A}_{12} & \mathbf{A}_{11} \end{bmatrix},$$

and therefore,

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_2 = (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} (\mathbf{S}'_2 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_2^F) + (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{21} \mathbf{x}_1 \\ \mathbf{p}_2 = (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} (\mathbf{B}'_{22} \boldsymbol{\pi}_2 + \mathbf{B}'_{12} \boldsymbol{\pi}_1) + (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_{12} \mathbf{p}_1 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

which completes the proof. \square

2.2 Exogenous and random agricultural supply

The decomposition just described allows the IO model to be reinterpreted in terms of two sectorial blocks, one of exogenous production and the other of endogenous production, with the production of the endogenous block being a function of the final demand of its own production and the supply of the exogenous production block.³ This new perspective is particularly useful for modeling the Argentine economy, which depends heavily on agricultural production. Versions (7) or (17) of the IO model make it possible to explain the supply of non-agricultural goods and services, say \mathbf{x}_2 in the expression (17), as a function of the demand of non-agricultural products and the supply of the agricultural sector \mathbf{x}_1 , which is not only exogenous, but also random.

The agricultural supply, due to its climatic dependence, is random and its probability distribution is unknown, although we can assume as a first approximation that it is multivariate normal, that is, $\mathbf{x}_1 \sim N(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_1}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1})$. Then, \mathbf{x}_2 is also normal with parameters

$$\begin{cases} E(\mathbf{x}_2) = (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} (\mathbf{S}'_2 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_2^F + \mathbf{A}_{21} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_1}) \\ var(\mathbf{x}_2) = (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{21} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1} \mathbf{A}'_{21} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

The price-dual version is analogous to the previous one, but defining $\mathbf{p}_1 \sim N(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_1}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1})$. So the parameters of the endogenous-block price distribution are

$$\begin{cases} E(\mathbf{p}_2) = (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} (\mathbf{B}'_{22} \boldsymbol{\pi}_2 + \mathbf{B}'_{12} \boldsymbol{\pi}_1) + (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_{12} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_1} \\ var(\mathbf{p}_2) = (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}'_{22})^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_{12} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1} \mathbf{A}_{12} (\mathbf{I}_{k-r} - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

A major critique to the IO model is that production and prices are not linked through a proper supply function. Introducing a covariance relationship between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{p} solves this problem, since the conditional expectation $E(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{p})$ leads to a kind of supply function

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{p}} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_1} \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_2} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{p}_1} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1 \mathbf{p}_2} \\ \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_2 \mathbf{p}_1} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_2 \mathbf{p}_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{p}_2} \\ \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2 \mathbf{p}_1} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_1 - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_1} \\ \mathbf{p}_2 - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

³Przybyliński, M. and A. Gorzałczyński (2022) proposed recently a decomposition of the IO model that discriminates domestic and import prices. Their model can be interpreted as a particular case of (7), with the matrix of technical coefficients associated with import prices being completely analogous to the block \mathbf{A}'_{21} of (7)

In other words, we postulate the existence of a covariance relationship between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{p} (represented by $cov(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}) = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{p}}$) whereby the equilibrium between quantities and prices occurs at the level of expected values and not at the current values level. The matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{p}}$ is not symmetric in general but its diagonal elements should be positive to reflect correctly the expected relationship between prices and quantities in a typical supply function. Then, it can be inferred that the estimation of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}}$ is crucial for this version of the IO model to have any empirical value. We will get back to this point later.

To decompose (20) in separate equations for each sectorial block we may invert the covariance matrix de prices going back to the formulas given by Tzon- Tzer et al. (2002)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2} \\ \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_1} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{11} & -\mathbf{U}_{11}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1} \\ -\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}\mathbf{U}_{11} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_1}\mathbf{U}_{11}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\mathbf{U}_{11} = \left(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_1} \right)^{-1}$, if such inverse exists. Then, operating algebraically, the expected supply for the first sector block is

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_1}|\mathbf{p} &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_1} + (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{p}_1} - \mathbf{H})\mathbf{U}_{11}(\mathbf{p}_1 - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_1}) + \\ &+ [\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{p}_2} - (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{p}_2} - \mathbf{H})\mathbf{U}_{11}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}]\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}_2 - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_2}) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{H} = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_1\mathbf{p}_2}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_1}$. The supply of the second sectorial block is obtained in a similar fashion and has the form

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_2}|\mathbf{p} &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_2} + (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_2\mathbf{p}_1} - \mathbf{H}_1)\mathbf{U}_{11}(\mathbf{p}_1 - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_1}) + \\ &+ [\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_2\mathbf{p}_2} - (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_2\mathbf{p}_1} - \mathbf{H}_2)\mathbf{U}_{11}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}]\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}_2 - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{p}_2}) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_1 = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_2\mathbf{p}_2}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}$ and $\mathbf{H}_2 = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}_2\mathbf{p}_2}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_1}$. Logically, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_1} = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}'_{\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2}$. In short, the expected production is explained as a linear combination of the equilibrium supply plus that driven by the deviation of prices from the equilibrium level.

3. Computing the Agricultural Technical Coefficients

Argentina's System of National Accounts (SNA) uses a hybrid classification of economic activities or sectors in which agriculture is classified by product while the rest of the sectors are properly classified by activity. A classification of the agricultural sector consistent with the one of the other sectors would imply the the current sectorial disaggregation (by product) be reclassified by type of company. That is, to replace the current supply and demand columns of the agricultural sector in the TSU by $\mathbf{S}_1^* = \mathbf{S}_1\mathbf{W}$ and $\mathbf{D}_1^* = \mathbf{D}_1\mathbf{W}$, respectively, where \mathbf{W} is a $k \times q$ array of product weights by company type. It can be shown that this transformation leads to the following version of the formula (7)

$$\mathbf{x}_1^* = (\mathbf{I}_q - \mathbf{W}'\mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}(\mathbf{W}'\mathbf{S}_1'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{d}_1^F) + (\mathbf{I}_q - \mathbf{W}'\mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{W}'\mathbf{A}_{12}\mathbf{x}_2 \quad (23)$$

The above expression is useful to estimate $E(\mathbf{x}_1^*) = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}_1}^*$ from data available in the SNA, specially for the accounts' base year. For that particular year \mathbf{x}_2 and \mathbf{d}_1^F are known, but not \mathbf{A}_{11} as the national agricultural census poll does not include questions on input-output relationships. Therefore, \mathbf{A}_{11} must be estimated from the available engineering knowledge. The methodology we propose to that end, and to compute \mathbf{W} , is as follows.

- In the first instance, detailed *gross margins* are elaborated from agronomic sources. Gross margins are essentially budgets of direct expenses and gross income per hectare at a crop or livestock product level, for example wheat, beef, milk, etc. These margins are elaborated based on the best available technical knowledge on input-product relationships (assuming favorable production situations) and for different production regions and technologies.⁴ From an economic point of view, *gross margins* understood as a production plan are comparable to Leontief-type production functions.
- Inputs and outputs of each gross margin are classified by *task* or *labor* (e.g. fallow, planting, pest and weed control, harvesting, etc.) and by the input involved, including agricultural machinery services and manual labor if any. Both inputs and outputs are classified following UNSTAT's five-digit Central Product Classification (CPC 1.1), while labor is classified according to an own classification. The codes of both classifications are combined into one to handle one single classification.
- The second stage is to summarize all the gross margins of the same crop or livestock into a single representative expense structure. To that end, a consensus production plan is sought through the solution of a linear program that minimizes the distance between all the production alternatives of the same crop, but guaranteeing some elementary conditions of economic viability, for example, that expenses do not exceed income. The analytic form of the program is $\min\{\mathbf{0}'\mathbf{d}^* + \mathbf{1}'\mathbf{e}\}$ subject to system constraints

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{u}' & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{u}' \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d}^* \\ \mathbf{e}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{e}_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_1 \\ \mathbf{d}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_m \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{1}'\mathbf{d}^* \leq 1, \quad (24)$$

where \mathbf{e} is a vector of errors or discrepancies, $\mathbf{u}' = [-1, 1]$, and $\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \dots$ are vectors of input shares on the total income. Each crop or livestock has m alternative production alternatives. Recall that the share of each expense in companies that maximize profits is equal to the elasticity of the corresponding input. At the end of this stage, a single expense structure is obtained for each crop or livestock. Vector \mathbf{d}^* is analogous to any column of the matrix $\mathbf{D}_1 \mathbf{T}_k^{-1}$.

- The third stage aims to define a typology of agricultural companies based on the features of the average farm of each district. To do this, cropland and livestock stocks of every county are compiled from the 2018 Agricultural Census. As livestock stocks are not additive to each other, nor to cropland, they must first be converted to grazing livestock units or GLU in order to compute the average stocking rate for each county.⁵ Then each type of cattle is converted to area units just dividing the county's GLU by the average stocking rate to get the theoretical area devoted to each livestock. Then, the

⁴Speaking properly, the gross margin is the difference between gross income and direct expenses, but by extension the whole income and expense spreadsheet is called so.

⁵The stocking rate is simply the quotient between the sum of the GLU of cattle, sheep, goats and horses, and the area of pastures and natural grasslands in the district. It's unit is GLU per hectare. The area of natural grasslands is computed as the difference between the total area of the district and the cultivated area, included pastures.

vector of shares of land devoted to every crop or livestock constitutes the vector of features of the average farm of each county.

- In the last stage, all average farm are grouped in clusters by means of the k -means clustering algorithm. Basically, this algorithm groups the average farms according to their distance to the closest typical company. The distance is computed in the quadratic norm. As a byproduct the algorithm returns the centroids \mathbf{w}_j of each cluster, which are simply the feature-vectors of each type of company. The centroids are hypothetical companies that minimize the sum of all distances within each cluster and among clusters. The matrix of centroids \mathbf{W} is the classification matrix we seek in order to convert \mathbf{A}_{11} from the second stage into an analogous matrix, but classified by type of company.

4. Final Comment

The preceding paper presents a decomposition of the IO model useful for various purposes. One of them is to update the supply vector of certain sectors keeping the supply of the others fixed. Another purpose, perhaps the most important one, is to “exogenize” the supply of some sectors of the model. Recall that, in the original IO model, sectorial supply is completely endogenous and is determined exclusively by shocks on the demand side. This order of causality, however, does not describe correctly the role of some sectors in the economy, such as agriculture whose supply relies more on the provision of certain natural resources (e.g. rainfall) than on the final demand of its products. In this sense, the representations given by (7) and (17) would be a more realistic option than the traditional representation.

Frank (2022) identified a bias in the projections of the IO model caused by the omission of natural resources and proposed an expansion of the TSU to handle this problem. That is, he proposed the addition of an extra column in the TSU to account for the provision and absorption of resources and called this new “sector” *Land*. The solution, however, presented its complexities because both the provision and the absorption of NR, and the technical relationship between those resources and agricultural production are usually unknown, at least at a national scale. The IO model with exogenous supply avoids this drawback, although it has its own limitations.

The main one is that the NR shock underlying production must affect only some sectors and in these sectors it must be stronger than any shock on the demands of its own-products. If this were not the case, i.e. almost all supply were exogenous or demand shocks cannot be ignored, the proposed model could become meaningless because of the confused effects of shocks on both sides of the equation. In this case, the NR model proposed in 2022 would be the only possible representation for such economy.

A major critique of the IO model (Schuschny 2005, p. 21) is that production and prices are not linked through a supply function because prices are built upon a sum of costs instead of a walrasian market clearing scheme. The introduction of a stochastic relationship between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{p} overcomes this drawback as the conditional expectation $E(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})$ leads indeed to a supply function. However, the structure of $\Sigma_{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{p}}$ is yet unknown. Elucidating this structure is beyond the scope of these notes and remains an open question.

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